

Intelligent Trust and Security Orchestration for 6G Distributed Cloud Environments

Deliverable 2.3 Policy Modelling, Enactment and Explainability for Trustworthy 6G Networks

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List of Acronyms

3GPP	3rd Generation Partnership Project
6G	Sixth Generation mobile network
AAA	Authentication, Authorization, and Accounting
ABAC	Attribute-based Access Control
AES	Advanced Encryption Standard
CA	Certification Authority
CRYSTALS-Dilithium	<i>CRYSTALS-Dilithium</i> is a lattice-based digital signature scheme whose security is based on the hardness of finding short vectors in lattices.
CRYSTALS-Kyber	A secure Key-Encapsulation Mechanism (KEM), relies on the challenge of solving the learning-with-errors (LWE) problem over module lattices for its security
DLT	Distributed Ledger Technology
ETSI	European Telecommunications Standards Institute
HLP	High-Level Policy
IBN	Intent-Based Networking
IdP	Identity Provider
IETF	Internet Engineering Task Force
JSON	JavaScript Object Notation
JWT	JSON Web Token
KEM	Key-Encapsulation Mechanism
LDAP	Lightweight Directory Access Protocol
LLMs	Large Language Models
LWE	Learning-With-Errors
MFA	Multi-Factor Authentication
MLN	Markov Logic Networks
MLP	Medium-Level Policy
NIST	National Institute of Standards and Technology (U.S. Dep of Commerce)
OAM	Operation, Administration and Maintenance
PaC	Policy-as-Code (PaC)
PAP	Policy Administration Point
PDP	Policy Decision Point
PEP	Policy Enforcement Point
PKI	Public Key Infrastructure
PQC	Post-quantum cryptography
RAM	Risk Assessment Module
RBAC	Role-based Access Control
RMF	Risk Management Framework
SBOM	Software Bill Of Materials
SotA	State of the Art
TAL	Transparent Accounting Ledger
TER	Transparent Evidence Repository
VPN	Virtual Private Network
WIMSE	Workload Identity in Multi-Service Environments
WP	Work Package
XAI	Explainable AI
ZTA	Zero-Trust Architecture

Executive Summary

This document, iTrust6G D2.3, is focused on identifying the technology foundations for the application of policies to the trustworthiness issue in future mobile networks, as well as on the proposal of the functional principles for this application, dealing with the issues related to how policies are expressed (modelling), applied (enactment) and analyzed (explainability).

The document is structured according to the four main pillars associated with these issues: trust models and their design for modelling, intent declarations to translate these models into enforceable policy rules, the enforcement mechanisms for enactment, and the techniques required to provide useful explanations of policy applications.

The foundation for trust modelling in iTrust6G is the zero-trust architecture (ZTA), based on the essential principles of (future-proof) encryption, (orchestration-based) automation, micro-segmentation, and transparency, together with an adequate use of AI techniques. The use of intent declarations, their lifecycle and main characteristics are then analysed, with a special emphasis on the application of these declarations to express security expectations by users and constraints by network admins.

The means for policy enforcement, based on AAA (Authentication, Authorization and Accounting) with identity at the core of it, are described, considering the relevance of non-human identities, given the whole ZTA is based on the capacity of properly identifying and assessing any element on the network, and with the relating of their identities to policy rules and to any evidence about the identified entity. With this goal of clearly associate the relevant evidence with the element identity, the use of a *Transparent Evidence Repository* (TER), populated by the different evaluation and assessment mechanisms in the iTrust6G architecture, and available to the policy decision mechanisms, is defined. This TER, in combination with the active policy rules and a *Transparent Accounting Ledger* (TAL), constitute the core of the policy decision mechanism.

Finally, the application of techniques to facilitate the auditability and explainability is discussed. Auditability is guaranteed by the dynamic nature of the TER and by the comprehensive accounting via the TAL. These two elements provide a transparent record, suitable to be exposed to third parties, associating every policy decision to the relevant identities, evidence and active policy rules. In a similar way, explainability relies on the use of the accounting log and on the capacity of “rolling back” the policy translation process, so the root policy declaration for each decision can be identified and used in providing an explanation to it.

1 Introduction

Policy application in the iTrust6G architecture is associated to the three functions identified in the title of this document, depicted in Figure 1-1 as the following:

- **Modelling** comprises the conceptual task of identifying the guidelines to be applied to achieve the desired security degree for the target network service or environment. Based on an analysis of relevant threats, feasible evaluation procedures and information sources, and suitable orchestration mechanisms, the network security admins can establish these principles. Modelling implies two kind of policy guidelines: those related to trust, establishing patterns and thresholds to decide on the trustworthiness of a given network element in a given environment, and those related to remediation, describing the behavior to be followed in case security risks or actual breaches are detected.
- **Enactment** implies the application of the policy guidelines to a given situation, usually termed as policy decision. Policy decisions are driven by two main levers: identity, so every entity involved in a particular decision is uniquely identified, and evidence, allowing to make the most complete evaluation possible of the status of such entity. It is worth noting that this identity-centric approach requires to identify any individual entity in the network environment, whatever its nature, and to relate them. Moreover, each evidence must be associated with a specific identity to support proper decisions.
- **Explainability** comprises the support for auditing processes, able to guarantee the evaluation of the decisions and related actions in the light of the applicable models and evidence. Different levels of such auditing can be considered, depending on the goals of the process and level of detail of the expected analysis. These auditing process must rely on a detailed trace of the applicable models, the involved identities and the relevant evidence for each decision.

Figure 1-1: Main policy functions and their connection with the iTrust6G system architecture

These three functions are connected by data flows that define a loop, whereas human-oriented policy models have to be translated into machine-readable policy rules to be applied in trust evaluation and orchestration for their enactment, and then analysed back to provide a connection of the enactment results with the human-oriented policy models when explanations are required.

This modelling-enactment-explanation loop interacts with the other elements in the iTrust6G architecture by providing policy decisions, applied by the enforcement points. All these other elements are expected to provide data in form of evidence to be applied as input for the decisions process. To complete the loop via explainability, a comprehensive accounting log is kept by the policy decision functions.

Figure 1-1 also illustrates these data flows and the modelling-enactment-explanation loop, associating the different functions with the elements described in the general iTrust6G architecture introduced in iTrust6G D2.2 [1]. As shown in the figure, Modelling and Explainability belong to the Policy Administration element, while Enactment is the main function of the Static and Dynamic Trust Assessment module, as described in iTrust6G D2.2.

1.1 Scope of the document

This document constitutes an initial analysis and design of the iTrust6G components involved in these three policy application functions. Based on this design, early technology evaluation, implementation, and integration work will start. From the experience gained in this work, together with a deeper understanding of the target use cases and requirements, work on a final version of the design will be produced and integrated with the final iTrust6G architecture. This initial design will be used as base for standards contributions and dissemination, which will be further updated as the design evolves.

iTrust6G D2.3 is directly related to project Technical Objective 1 (*Design an End-to-End system security architecture that capitalizes on zero-trust principles to enable a trustworthy 6G service management platform, addressing dynamic network and application-level security requirements*), and it constitutes an essential enabler for Technical Objective 3 (*Conceive novel Trust Algorithms (TA) exploiting AI integrated into trust management system (TM) accounting for forensics evidence*) and Technical Objective 5 (*Specify, develop and integrate intent-based security policies/engine, for explainable and automated E2E security orchestration*).

1.2 Structure of the deliverable

iTrust6G D2.3 is structured according to the four main technology pillars associated with the three functions given title the document:

1. The trust models and their design for modelling.
2. The intent declarations that are used to express these models and later translate them into enforceable policy rules, bridging the gap between modelling and the functions it shapes.
3. The enforcement mechanisms for enactment.
4. The techniques required to provide useful explanations of policy applications.

For each one of these technology pillars, the document first provides in Section 2 an analysis of the foundations for them, going into the relevant architectural considerations and design guidelines applicable to each one in the subsequent sections. Some conclusions and indications for further refinement of the design are provided in the final section.

1.3 Relation to other WPs and tasks

The use of ZTA for network security enhancement is one of the main mottos of iTrust6G. The ZTA enabler functions proposed in this document rely on the requirements introduced by iTrust6G D2.1. Policy administration and trust assessment are at the core of the iTrust6G architecture, as described in iTrust6G D2.2, and play a key role in the configuration and information flows of the elements to be designed and implemented within the development work packages (WP3, WP4 and WP5), and will be validated by means of WP6. All these work packages will provide the necessary feedback to improve the design guidelines proposed here in the upcoming iTrust6G D2.4. In addition, these guidelines will be made available as part of scientific communications and contributed as seen appropriate to industrial and standardization initiatives.

2 Technology Foundations

2.1 Trust models

Trust models are a critical component for establishing security and reliability in modern network administration practices. Therefore, they constitute key mechanisms for the operation, administration and maintenance (OAM) of next-generation 6G networks, particularly for the core components envisioned in the iTrust6G project. Current state-of-the-art (SotA) trust models aim to address the complex challenges posed by the distributed, heterogeneous, and dynamic nature of 6G environments.

One key focus area is ZTA (ZTA), which assumes no implicit trust and requires continuous verification of every access request. ZTA principles are being adapted for 6G networks to provide fine-grained access control and dynamic trust evaluation across multi-stakeholder and multi-domain environments. This aligns closely with iTrust6G's objectives for intelligent trust and security orchestration [2].

The current standard and framework most relevant to implement ZTA in 6G networks can be considered NIST SP 800-207 [3]. NIST's Special Publication 800-207 provides comprehensive guidelines for implementing ZTA, based on a number of fundamentals principles illustrated in Figure 2-1. While originally developed for enterprise networks, its principles are being adapted for public networks and can be consequently applied to 6G. It focuses on continuous verification of identity and device health, ubiquitous deployment of the least privilege access principle, strong and small and large network segmentation and continuous monitoring and analytics. In iTrust6G, the consideration on a set of aspects will be specifically relevant, as discussed below.

2.1.1 Future-proof encryption

Current SotA encryption methods, such as AES (Advanced Encryption Standard) for symmetric encryption and RSA or ECC (Elliptic Curve Cryptography) for asymmetric encryption, can serve as a starting point for securing 6G communications. These algorithms, when implemented with sufficiently large key sizes and proper key management practices, can provide strong security for the near term. To make encryption truly future-proof for 6G networks, it's crucial to design systems with crypto-agility in mind, allowing for seamless transitions to post-quantum encryption algorithms when they become necessary. This approach involves implementing a modular cryptographic architecture that can easily swap out current encryption algorithms for quantum-resistant ones without disrupting network operations or requiring extensive system overhauls.

Figure 2-1: ZTA fundamentals

For example, hybrid schemes that combine current algorithms with post-quantum candidates can be implemented, allowing for a gradual transition. As NIST finalizes its post-quantum cryptography standards, algorithms like CRYSTALS-Kyber for key encapsulation and CRYSTALS-Dilithium for digital signatures can be integrated into existing cryptographic frameworks [4]. This strategy ensures that 6G networks can maintain strong encryption even in the face of future quantum computing threats, while also adhering to the zero trust principles of continuous verification and least privilege access.

2.1.2 Automation and orchestration

Automation and orchestration face significant challenges in 6G networks due to the massive volume of data and events that need to be processed in real-time. AI-enabled trust algorithms represent an important SotA development to address these issues. These algorithms leverage machine learning techniques to evaluate trust based on multiple factors like identity, behavior, context, and historical data [5], enabling more adaptive and nuanced trust decisions compared to traditional static models. However, the sheer scale and velocity of data in 6G environments can overwhelm even advanced AI systems. iTrust6G aims to further advance this field by integrating AI-driven trust evaluation with forensic evidence and cyber threat intelligence, while developing novel approaches to handle the unprecedented data volumes and event rates expected in 6G networks. This includes distributed processing architectures, edge computing, and advanced data filtering techniques to enable real-time trust decisions at scale [6].

2.1.3 Micro segmentation

Micro-segmentation offers a granular security model that aligns well with the ZTA principles essential for 6G. By dividing the network into smaller, isolated segments, micro-segmentation can enhance security, reduce attack surfaces, and enable fine-grained access control in 6G environments. This approach is particularly crucial given the diverse range of devices and services expected in 6G, from IoT sensors to holographic communications. Researchers have highlighted the potential of micro-segmentation in 6G to support network slicing, a key feature that allows multiple virtual networks to coexist on a shared physical infrastructure. Furthermore, micro-segmentation can facilitate the implementation of AI-driven security policies, which are essential for enabling effective threat containment and rapid incident response, critical for maintaining the ultra-high reliability required in 6G applications. Micro-segmentation can support the dynamic and flexible nature of 6G networks, allowing for real-time adjustments to security policies based on changing network conditions and threat landscapes [7].

For micro-segmentation to work, the underlying infrastructure must provide the capabilities to create unique network segments, that can be protected by gateways, next generation firewalls, or other security devices that allow for network security enforcing. Traditionally it was done in central choke points, such as firewalls or managed routers. But for 6G networks it might be unfeasible to do so and require distributed devices that can act as de facto gateways, and serve as the policy enforcement points.

2.1.4 Transparency and integrity

Distributed ledger technology is being explored to enhance trust in decentralized 6G ecosystems. Distributed ledger systems can provide tamper-resistant records of interactions and enable transparent, verifiable trust establishment between multiple parties. This is relevant for iTrust6G's goals of secure multi-tenancy support and trust management across distributed cloud environments. Some key benefits include:

- Immutable audit trails: All network interactions and trust evaluations can be recorded on a blockchain, creating a tamper-proof historical record.
- Decentralized trust: No single authority controls the ledger, enabling trust between multiple parties without a central intermediary.

- Smart contracts: Automated trust policies and service level agreements can be encoded and enforced via smart contracts.
- Public verifiability: The blockchain ledger can be made publicly accessible, allowing external auditing and verification of trust decisions and network operations.
- Process transparency: Making the steps and methodologies used in algorithmic decision-making visible, allowing users to comprehend how outcomes are derived.
- Open Documentation: Providing comprehensive documentation of system architecture, data sources, and algorithmic processes to facilitate understanding and scrutiny.
- Data Transparency: Clearly disclosing data collection methods, usage policies, and data governance practices to ensure users are informed about how their data is handled.

2.1.5 Segmented software defined networks

Software Defined Networking represents an approach to network management that fundamentally changes how networks are configured and controlled. At its core, SDN decouples the network control plane (decision-making) from the data plane (packet forwarding), enabling more dynamic and programmatic network configuration.

This separation allows network administrators to manage network services through abstraction of lower-level functionality, making the network more cloud-like in its flexibility and efficiency compared to traditional network management approaches.

The SDN architecture consists of three primary layers that work in concert to enable programmable network control.

- The Application Layer sits at the top, housing systems like intrusion detection, load balancing, and firewalls that can be managed through the controller without requiring additional tools.
- The Control Layer acts as the brain of the system, containing the SDN controller that translates requirements between applications and infrastructure using protocols like OpenFlow.
- The Infrastructure Layer forms the foundation, comprising the physical and virtual network devices that handle packet data flows according to instructions received from the controller [8].

A key strength of SDN lies in its centralized management approach through the SDN Controller, which maintains a global view of the network while appearing to applications as a single, logical switch.

This centralization enables network administrators to configure, manage, and optimize network resources rapidly through dynamic, automated programs.

The controller must be carefully secured and protected since it represents a critical point of control - if compromised through attacks like DDoS, the entire network could be affected.

When combined with Network Function Virtualization (NFV), SDN creates a more adaptable and resilient network architecture capable of supporting diverse applications while maintaining security through features like micro-segmentation and AI-driven security policies.

This software-based approach allows operators to dynamically configure their networks to support varying regional and temporal demands, making it particularly valuable for the complex requirements of next-generation wireless networks.

2.1.6 Authentication and access control

Modern authentication and access control systems are increasingly adopting ZTA principles, which represent a fundamental shift from traditional perimeter-based security models. This approach assumes no implicit trust and requires continuous verification of every access request, regardless of the source's location or previous trust status. The NIST SP 800-207 framework provides comprehensive guidelines for implementing these robust authentication mechanisms, focusing on continuous verification of identity and device health monitoring.

The implementation of authentication in modern networks relies heavily on multiple layers of verification and continuous monitoring. The system enforces least privilege access principles, ensuring that users and devices only have access to the specific resources they need for their tasks. This is complemented by strong network segmentation, both at small and large scales, which helps contain potential security breaches and limits the blast radius of any successful attack.

These security measures are particularly crucial in multi-stakeholder and multi-domain environments, where traditional trust boundaries become increasingly blurred. AI-enabled trust algorithms have emerged as a critical component in modern authentication systems, evaluating multiple factors including identity, behaviour, context, and historical data to make more nuanced and adaptive access control decisions. These algorithms leverage machine learning techniques to process massive volumes of data in real-time, enabling dynamic trust evaluation that goes beyond static, rule-based approaches.

The integration of AI-driven trust evaluation with forensic evidence and cyber threat intelligence provides a more comprehensive security posture, allowing systems to adapt to emerging threats and changing network conditions. These technologies enable real-time trust decisions at scale, which is essential for handling the unprecedented data volumes and event rates expected in modern networks.

2.1.7 Trust model properties

Modern trust models applying AI emphasize the robustness and reliability of algorithms. This involves the following:

- **Robustness and Security:** Ensuring algorithms are resilient to adversarial attacks and can maintain performance under varying conditions.
- **Fairness and Bias Mitigation:** Implementing techniques to detect and reduce biases in data and algorithms, promoting equitable outcomes across diverse user groups.
- **Accountability:** Establishing clear responsibility for algorithmic decisions, enabling traceability and auditability of processes and outcomes.

Furthermore, these trust models often integrate algorithmic integrity, transparency, and explainability to create comprehensive trust frameworks. Examples include:

- **Explainable AI (XAI):** Techniques that make AI decision-making processes transparent and understandable without compromising performance [9].
- **Trustworthy AI frameworks:** Comprehensive guidelines and standards that encompass ethical considerations, transparency, fairness, and accountability in AI systems [10].
- **Federated learning:** Approaches that enhance data privacy and transparency by decentralizing data processing, allowing models to learn from distributed data sources without centralized data collection. Some advanced approaches combine traditional knowledge-based systems with machine learning techniques. Markov logic networks (MLNs) integrated with external knowledge

extracted by Large Language Models (LLMs) and automated knowledge extraction to enhance explainability in medical decision-making.

For the IoT and edge computing aspects of 6G, lightweight trust models suitable for resource-constrained devices are being developed. These often employ fuzzy logic or simplified machine learning to enable trust decisions at the network edge [11]. iTrust6G's work on programmable interfaces and security-as-a-service can build upon these edge-centric trust frameworks.

Continuous trust assessment and dynamic policy enforcement are other important SotA trends. These enable real-time adaptation to changing network conditions and threat landscapes. iTrust6G's focus on AI-enabled end-to-end security orchestration and anomaly detection aligns well with this direction [12].

2.2 Intent declarations and policy frameworks

2.2.1 Intent-based networking

A critical research area is the security orchestration of next-generation networks, to ensure that security requirements mandated by business constraints or applicable regulations are met. Various paradigms and approaches are gaining traction to address these new challenges, including zero-touch networks and intent-based networks. In these paradigms, the entire network lifecycle is system-managed, minimizing human involvement and reducing misconfigurations. Zero-touch networks are fully automated networks requiring no manual intervention during the whole lifecycle, including initial provisioning, configuration, and maintenance.

Intent-based networking (IBN) is a recent paradigm that has its foundation on the principle of enforcing behaviors rather than configurations [13]. The IBN paradigm expects that the intended behaviors are defined at a high level rather than specifying low-level network configurations, which should (theoretically) replace or drastically reduce the need for manual intervention on the network infrastructure. Moreover, IBN expects deviations from the intended network operations to be automatically addressed to reconduct the system to the desired behavior and bring the state back to functioning. IBN can be seen as an advancement over traditional policy-based network management, with the introduction of dynamic mechanisms for intelligent management of network resources through observability.

IBN integrates well with software-defined networking (SDN) principles, which represents a shift from traditional, manually configured, hardware-centric networks to programmable, software-driven solutions that minimize or eliminate the need for manual management.

A key feature of IBN is its use of a controller abstraction to create a management layer that serves as a central control point for all network activities. While this approach aligns with existing SDN architectures, IBN extends beyond them by incorporating intelligence and higher-level requirements into network orchestration and automation. In practice, and often in normative architecture specifications, this role is typically handled by different sub-layers or components, each responsible for specific tasks. This enables network administrators to define overarching business and service objectives, translate them into specific policies, and optimize the network to meet these goals.

IBN has garnered significant interest in the telco industry, where flexibility is essential for efficient service requirements and operations. IBN sees several standardization initiatives by several standards organizations. While the paradigm has been taking shape through independent and non-structured implementations and research, several standardization initiatives have been established to define specifications and interfaces for which the different implementations should be aligned. For instance, the IRTF depicted the main processes and workflows employed in working IBN frameworks from an architectural level [14]. In the IRTF RFC, the IBN management approach is described as a closed control loop in which the main stages are fulfilment one,

which concerns the actual deployment of intent into its resulting configuration and network resources, and the assurance stage, which instead focuses on all the activities which must be conducted to keep the existing resources running and avoiding conflicts in the way they are managed through intents. Then, the 3GPP specification was provided, and the specification proposed by ETSI TS 128 312 was implemented.

Moreover, the ETSI ZSM defined the Principles of Intent as:

1. Intent establishes machine-processable knowledge.
2. Intent is declarative, so it leaves any implementation detail internal to the solution provider.
3. Intent is focused on expectations of the results for the consumer.
4. Intent is formally expressed so it is machine-processable and readable for humans.
5. Intent supports complete automation of intent owner-intent handler interactions as well as of intent-defined service delivery.

2.2.2 Intent lifecycle

Specifying Intents is the first challenge; it has been addressed in the literature, several languages and frameworks have been proposed in the literature [14][15]. The lifecycle for applying intent to network services in general, and therefore to security in particular is shown in Figure 2-2.

At the design level, IBN can be seen as comprising two broad control loops. The first is the **intent fulfilment** loop, which encompasses all the processes that produce the actual low-level configurations and service deployments, starting from a high-level intent. The first task within this loop involves the specification and ingestion of intents provided by users and service administrators [18]. Next, there will be translation mechanisms that transform, or “render”, high-level intents into concrete configurations, often by leveraging abstract models of the services. Recently, AI, particularly LLM, has been applied to provide a semantic interpretation of the intents [19]. This task is followed by orchestration, ensuring the actions are executed to achieve the desired state in the operational environment.

Figure 2-2: A typical IBN lifecycle [17]

The second control loop, known as **intent assurance**, focuses on continuously and periodically verifying that the state of the services remains aligned with the objectives defined in the intents. This loop ensures potential conflicts or inconsistencies are identified, resolved, and reported to the user. A key element in this process is monitoring, which provides the necessary information to assess the status of services and the operational environment. Monitoring enables comparisons between the actual and expected states, helping to identify discrepancies. Additional processes are then required to resolve misalignments, ensuring that the network meets the specified intents.

2.3 Policy enforcement

Effective policy enforcement is a critical aspect of access control mechanisms in modern systems, ensuring that security policies governing resource and service access are consistently applied, and able to support an appropriate trustworthiness assessment for those resources and services, together with the user entities attempting to access them, supporting a comprehensive *trust fabric* weaving all the elements in the network. This section explores the foundational technologies used for the exchange of information to be applied in policy enforcement, focusing on JSON Web Token (JWT) and the key protocols it supports, such as OAuth 2.0 and OpenID Connect.

All these technologies rely on the use of unique, persistent identifiers for any entity, and the availability of a number of *attributes* associated to that identifier. The effective association of an entity with one of those identifiers allows policy enforcement elements to access the required attributes associated with them, in a process generally known as *authentication*. Policy rules are expressed in terms of these attributes and their values, and their application to a given entity via its associated attributes is commonly referred as *authorization*. OpenID Connect is an authentication protocol, tightly related to the authorization mechanisms provided by OAuth 2.0, and both use JWT as the format to transfer data, essentially identifiers and attributes, plus crypto material to provide means for verifying properties such as integrity, confidentiality and timeliness.

OAuth 2.0 is an industry-standard authorization protocol that plays a pivotal role in enforcing access control policies by allowing secure and delegated access to protected resources. It provides a framework for users to authorize third-party applications to act on their behalf without directly exposing sensitive credentials like passwords. By leveraging OAuth, organizations can enforce fine-grained access policies, ensuring that third-party applications are granted only the specific permissions necessary for the requested operations. This delegation of access follows strict policy guidelines that protect sensitive data and minimize the risk of unauthorized access [20].

OAuth enhances security by compartmentalizing access to user resources, ensuring that applications are only permitted to interact with the specified data or services. This enables organizations to enforce robust policies around user consent and privilege management, ensuring that even third-party applications operate within predefined security boundaries [21].

OpenID Connect, built on top of OAuth 2.0, adds an identity layer that enhances policy enforcement around authentication. It facilitates secure user authentication by utilizing an authorization server that provides identity verification and essential user profile information. This protocol is integral to modern identity management strategies, allowing for scalable, policy-driven access across diverse platforms and services [22].

JWT plays a key role in policy enforcement for both authentication and authorization by representing a set of claims in a compact, URL-safe format. JWTs are widely used in conjunction with OAuth 2.0 and OpenID Connect, ensuring secure token-based access control. The use of JWT allows organizations to enforce consistent access policies across multiple systems and applications [23].

JWT is especially important in the OAuth 2.0 framework because it enables secure, self-contained, and verifiable tokens that can be passed between parties efficiently. Its compact format allows for easy transmission, and the use of cryptographic signatures ensures token integrity and authenticity, eliminating the need for server-side token storage. Additionally, JWTs enable fine-grained access control by embedding claims such as user roles, scopes, and expiration times directly within the token, facilitating precise enforcement of access policies [24].

The integration of JWT with OAuth 2.0 and OpenID Connect offers a robust and scalable solution for enforcing access control and authentication policies in modern systems. JWT provides a secure, compact, and self-contained method for transmitting claims, while OAuth 2.0 governs the delegation of access, and OpenID Connect adds an essential identity layer. Together, these technologies allow organizations to implement fine-grained access controls, ensuring that security policies are consistently enforced across diverse systems and applications. The combined use of JWT, OAuth 2.0, and OpenID Connect enhances both security and performance, making them foundational components in today's identity and access management strategies.

2.4 Accountability and explainability

The accountability concept involves tracing and attributing actions or decisions to responsible entities within the system being accounted for, in our case a next-generation mobile network. Its absence implies, on the one hand, the exacerbation of well-known attacks such as IP spoofing, where the packet host cannot be traced, or Denial of Service (DoS), where the source of overwhelming traffic is obscured, making it difficult to identify and hold responsible the perpetrators behind these malicious activities. On the other hand, imperfect accountability precludes the deep analysis of security incidents, especially important to derive identification and mitigation patterns to address future incidents. A key component to holding responsible parties accountable is the integration of explainability guarantees, as they provide a clear and understandable rationale for actions of any kind: decisions, scores, access granting, etc. By addressing their inherent complexity, explainability techniques foster transparency, ultimately establishing policy-based mechanisms as the natural interface for automated management of complex network environments.

Future Beyond 5G (B5G) and 6G networks will connect vast numbers of devices and provide innovative services powered by AI and continuously evolving technologies. In this context, accountability ensures that if a system fails or malfunctions, the responsible parties—whether they are network operators, service providers, or an AI system—can be identified and held liable. This is crucial for maintaining trust, as users need assurance that there are mechanisms in place to address failures and that entities are responsible for their actions. At the same time, explainable systems ensure that stakeholders can comprehend how deployed systems and AI-driven decisions affect network operations, resource management and service delivery. For example, the recent development of O-RAN, which incorporates open RAN components and could be utilized by B5G and 6G networks, presents new accountability issues. In general, the operation and security of vendor-specific RANs were centralized under the responsibility of a single vendor, therefore ensuring accountability. However, with O-RAN, the process of breaking down hardware and software into independent components from several vendors requires the allocation of responsibility throughout the whole supply chain and network structure. Therefore, some auditing procedures could be employed to ensure accountability in such networks.

More specifically for the AI systems that are involved in a modern B5G and 6G infrastructure, accountability as a metric can be “decomposed” into multiple sub-metrics, namely “currentness”, “feature importance”, “stability”, “compacity” and “consistency”, all measuring different aspects of the eXplainable AI (XAI) techniques describing the system. This viewpoint enhances the interrelated connection of the two in contemporary SotA approaches [25].

Some auditing mechanisms for accountability are as follow:

- Decentralized Auditing [26]: To provide accountability among various entities, a decentralized auditing mechanism is required. Moreover, by using blockchain-based auditing, resource allocations, service deployments, and other miscellaneous network configurations can be immutably stored. This can be achieved because every entity in such architectures can record its activities individually.
- Cross-Domain Auditing [27]: Since B5G and 6G network components are often distributed across multiple operators and vendors, cross-domain auditing is necessary to ensure consistent accountability. Systems must be able to perform end-to-end audits that encompass the full lifecycle of network operations, from RAN hardware to virtualized network functions (VNFs) at the core and edge.
- To satisfy accountability requirements, 6G networks must collect evidence of the various component actions [28]. Because such network architecture necessitates the collection of evidence from virtualized and disaggregated units across various manufacturers, interoperability standards must be in place to facilitate the easy exchange and verification of data.
- Evidence Chains [29] : Verification of network slices or Mobile Edge Computing (MEC) services require 6G systems to possess the ability to collect evidence from the user plane, control plane, and data plane, forming end-to-end evidence chains. Evidence obtained from the Data Unit (DU) and Resource Unit (RU) must be independently verified with evidence from the core network to guarantee responsibility throughout the whole service lifecycle.

Thus, accountability ensures that actions within complex, technology-driven networks are traceable and auditable. Furthermore, explainability enhances this by making decisions and processes transparent and understandable to human operators, allowing for greater oversight, trust, and adaptability in the increasingly decentralized and autonomous architecture of 6G networks:

A key function of transparency in such networks is to support human-in-the-loop (HTL) systems, where human operators oversee, audit and adjust to decisions made by automated processes. This is particularly important in zero-touch network configuration scenarios where systems manage networks autonomously manages yet human supervision is still required for rootcauseanalysis and troubleshooting [30]. In the next generation of networks, which is envisioned to consist of network elements that are highly decentralized, transparency will ensure that decisions are interpretable, transparent and traceable at the network edge, allowing for real-time adaptability and troubleshooting. This integration can play a key role in achieving networks that are self-optimizing and self-healing, where automated systems adjust to shifts in network demand or performance and human operators need to understand and trust these adjustments [31].

For these networks to function effectively, trust policies must be clearly defined to govern interactions among stakeholders. Towards this, establishing transparency guarantees upon trust policies can assist by converting natural language trust requirements into actionable, understandable behaviors.

Moreover, explainability allows the generation of counterfactual explanations, which show how slight changes to a user's context (e.g., different device type or time of access) could lead to different outcomes in the decision-making process, adding transparency to trust policies. This can be extremely helpful where security policies must adapt dynamically to different conditions. For example, stakeholders can see why a specific user was denied access and what conditions would need to be different for access to be granted, thereby increasing the system's accountability and clarity [32].

However, implementing explainability in complex systems presents various challenges, as making processes

more transparent can conflict with other system objectives. One key challenge is the trade-off between robustness and explainability; increasing transparency often requires simplifying models, which can reduce their resilience and accuracy. Conversely, highly robust systems may rely on intricate designs that are harder to interpret, making it difficult to understand or justify their decisions [33].

3 Trust Model Design

3.1 Trust relationships in the iTrust6G platform

In the iTrust6G platform, trust relationships between entities are foundational to ensuring secure, reliable, and efficient communication and operations across the 6G ecosystem. These relationships rely heavily on compliance assessments, ensuring that network components, infrastructure, and services meet predefined security and operational policies. Establishing trust based on compliance, continuously assessing the trustworthiness of network entities, and implementing robust technical mechanisms are needed to maintain trust in this highly distributed, multi-stakeholder environment.

This section presents how trust would be established through compliance assessments, continuously monitored, and technically implemented in the iTrust6G platform.

3.1.1 Establishing trust relationships

In the context of the iTrust6G platform, compliance is the network entity accordance to defined set of operational, security, and regulatory conformity policy requirements, as evaluated by the corresponding compliance checks. An entity's initial ability to establish trust is determined by how well it complies with these checks.

Trust establishment can be initiated with a conformity assessment. A conformity assessment process is the core of a trust relationship establishment. This process includes evaluating an entity against predefined security and operational criteria, often based on internationally recognized frameworks, such as: ISO/IEC 27001 [34], for information security management; NIST 800-53 [35], for security and privacy checks; and NIS2 Directive [36] requirements for network and information systems. In iTrust6G, a custom set of security references will be created to establish trust. Eventually, these compliance assessments will be designed to assess both the operational and technical aspects of a device. If the device passes the compliance tests, the trust establishment procedure should follow.

3.1.2 Continuous assessment of established trust relationships

Once the trust between the entity and the network is established, it needs to be continuously maintained through the session that the device is connected and possibly interacts with other devices. A trusted entity can become untrusted if its security posture changes. For that reason, continuous assessment mechanisms are required to ensure that the previously trusted entities remain compliant and trustworthy over time.

To achieve that, some security monitoring mechanisms should be implemented. Periodical vulnerability scans, patch management monitoring, and near-real-time threat detection could provide a clearer view on whether the trust score on a device remains. Such mechanisms are expected to provide specific scores to be aggregated into a general one. Additionally, the initial trust and compliance assessments will be repeated over time. Below, a basic set of compliance metrics is presented which is based on the initial implementation, that might change depending on the project evolution in the coming months:

- **Software Patch Compliance:** Depending on the software services that are installed on a device and how many of them are up to date, a threshold percentage could be established, and if lower than expected, a device might not be considered trusted.
- **Vulnerability Count:** The more vulnerabilities existent within a device, the lower the trust score could be.
- **Vendor Integrity Score:** Depending on supply chain checks, the installed software within a device could be scored based on the vendor's reputation. (e.g.: vulnerabilities per software they have released)

- **Hardware Component Provenance:** Again, based on supply chain checks, a hardware component a device might have could contain a vulnerability, and as a result, lower the overall trust score of the device.

3.1.3 Initial technical design of trust relationships

This subsection explores how the technical design of trust relationships could be initially planned. To begin with, a standard for establishing and verifying a trust establishment needs to be determined. Next, a strategy for preserving the relationship based on trust needs to be developed.

At first, trust anchors are used as a point of reference that provide root-level verification. Typical trust anchor implementations are based on a Public Key Infrastructure (PKI), using Certificate Authorities (CAs) to support trust links. CAs are used to verify the identity of entities and network components. Another approach to provide trust anchors is the use of Distributed Ledger Technology (DLT). The use of DLT in decentralized situations enables the storage of unchangeable records related to conformity assessments, security certifications, and operational performance. This mechanism offers a verifiable and decentralized trust anchor.

If the trust is established via the trust anchors, a trust link is created. Trust links are items that represent the trust among the given network elements. These links are generated, assessed, and, if required, withdrawn. There are several methodologies that could be utilized to implement such links:

- Mutual authentication protocols, such as OAuth, TLS (Transport Layer Security), or Zero Trust Network Access (ZTNA), are used to establish trust links over networks. These mechanisms guarantee that those participating in a communication channel can authenticate their identity to one another, together with the relevant security status attributes prior to proceeding with any interaction.
- Trust management using smart contracts involves the automated enforcement of trust agreements among entities. In the event that a network slice violates its service-level agreement (SLA), the smart contract has the capability to prompt the revocation of its access to specific network resources.
- A dynamic trust scoring system could assign a trust score to each entity by evaluating its performance, security posture, and conformity metrics in real-time. These scores vary depending on the ongoing evaluations and can activate automated reactions such as the reduction of trust, limitations on access, or even the implementation of quarantine measures in the event of suspicion.

Consequently, all those actions could be grouped conforming lifecycle for convenience. This lifecycle would include the following categories:

1. **Creation:** Initial compliance evaluations, confirmed identity, and successful mutual authentication form the foundation of the trust link.
2. **Monitoring:** Continuous monitoring of the link is done to detect any alterations in security posture or operational behavior.
3. **Evaluation:** Periodic re-evaluation of the trust link ensures that it remains valid.
4. **Revocation or Renewal:** If the entity's trust score falls below a critical threshold, the trust link can be revoked

3.2 Trust link lifecycle management

In the iTrust6G platform, trust link lifecycle management refers to the systematic procedures of establishing, maintaining, and renewing/terminating trust relationships between the involved entities in a 6G ecosystem.

Figure 3-1: Fundamentals of Trust Link Lifecycle Management in iTrust6G

These relationships of trust or trust links between users, systems, network functions, application functions, or devices are to ensure reliable and secure communication procedures following proper policies and security protocols. In the context of iTrust6G, regular monitoring and re-evaluation of the trust links (or trust link management) form a core part of zero-trust security models, where the trust needs to be continuously reassessed. Typically, the trust link lifecycle management procedures involve two main stages, as described in the next sections followed by fundamentals of trust link lifecycle management in Figure 3-1.

3.2.1 Establishing and renewing trust links

Establishing a trust link involves the creation of a secure and valid relationship between two or more entities, ensuring that they can exchange information or perform actions in a trusted manner. In a 6G ecosystem, the establishment of the trust links can be achieved using the following functionalities:

- **Identity Verification:** This involves authentication methods, such as cryptographically protected identifier verification based on pre-shared secret key, multi-factor authentication (MFA), or cryptographic certificates.
- **Authentication and Authorization:** The entities use credentials based on pre-provisioned cryptographic materials (e.g., symmetric key) or certificates to authenticate themselves, like those in PKI. Authorization based on managed subscribed services in case of end-users, or their devices are based on OAuth or local policy in case of network functions.
- **Trust Agreement:** This includes the use of standard integrity protection algorithms and confidentiality protection algorithms, for access stratum and non-access stratum level protection and over standard communication protocols.
- **Key Exchange:** Cryptographic keys, or certificates are often exchanged to facilitate secure communication. For example, two systems in the network may use a protocol like SSL/TLS to exchange encryption keys to establish a secure channel securely.

- **Trust Policy Enforcement:** the trust link is governed by policies that define the scope of trust. These policies could include access control, data formats, data handling rules (e.g., data protection at rest and in transit), security domain requirements, logging/auditing requirements etc.

When systems communicate across different security domain, policies can enforce intra domain and inter domain specific communication security requirements to ensure trusted links can still be established across inter domain communication with necessary additional security mechanism in place (e.g., security gateways and so on). Renewing a trust link ensures that the established relationship remains valid and secure over time, particularly when cryptographic keys or certificates expire, or security policies are updated. These renewal mechanisms imply the following steps:

- **Certificate/Key Renewal:** Trust links that rely on certificates (e.g., SSL/TLS) or cryptographic keys need periodic renewal before they expire. This ensures that trust is maintained without any interruption in communication.
- **Re-authentication and re-authorization:** Periodically, entities may be required to re-authenticate and re-authorize to confirm that they still meet the conditions of the trust agreement. This ensures that only legitimate and authorized entities continue to have access.
- **Re-assessment of Trust Conditions:** When renewing a trust link, policies or conditions may need to be reassessed. For example, user roles, security policies, or access privileges may have changed, requiring an update to the trust agreement. This is important in zero-trust environments where trust is dynamically and continuously validated.
- **Compliance and Auditing:** Renewing trust links often requires checking compliance with security policies and regulations (e.g., GDPR, HIPAA). Auditing and logging are typically part of this process to ensure transparency and accountability.
- **Handling Expiry or Revocation:** If a trust link expires or is revoked (due to security issues or role changes), renewal might involve going through the trust establishment process again, with updated credentials or certificates.

Using the ITrust6G platform for zero-trust management, we aim to solve the challenges in establishing and renewing Trust Links by monitoring, a) the Expiration of Certificates/Keys, b) Evolving Security Threats, and c) Scalability. In doing so, the ITrust6G platform will contribute to the processes that are critical in maintaining the integrity of the network systems and security of communication, data exchange, and access control across networks and systems as a part of establishing and renewing trust links.

3.2.2 Accounting and auditing trust links

In the ITrust6G platform, the trust relationships or trust links between entities in a 6G ecosystem must be functioning as intended, adhere to trust policies, and meet security standards. These also constitute transparency, traceability, and compliance with regulations by monitoring and recording activities related to trust links. This can be achieved through regular accounting and auditing of the trust links.

In the context of ITrust6G, accounting refers to keeping records of all actions and activities related to trust links, including their creation, maintenance, renewal, suspension, and termination. These records are used for further monitoring, resource allocation, and forensic analysis. The key elements for accounting of trust links can be listed as follows:

- **Logging Trust Link Activities:** Every interaction or change related to a trust link is logged that includes, a) when and how the trust link was established, b) who or what entities are part of the trust link, c) what operations were performed (e.g., key exchange, authentication), and d) how long the trust link is valid.
- **Resource Usage Monitoring:** Especially in cloud or network services in a 6G telco environment, some

trust links might be tied to resource consumption (e.g., bandwidth usage or API calls) where accounting records resource usage linked or footprints to specific trust relationships, which helps performance monitoring.

- **Tracking Expiry and Renewal:** Accounting ensures that expiration dates of certificates, keys, and other credentials are tracked so that renewals can be scheduled in advance to avoid service disruption.
- **Access Control Management:** All access events related to trust links should be accounted for, including any changes in permissions, role assignments, or trust policies. This helps ensure that unauthenticated or unauthorized access is identified, and trust links are only available to properly authenticated and authorized entities.

Auditing in a 6G ecosystem involves reviewing the logs and records of trust links to assess compliance, detect anomalies, and verify that security policies are being followed. It focuses on examining whether trust links are properly managed and secure over time. Auditing of the trust links can be done using:

- SIEM (Security Information and Event Management)/SOAR (Security Orchestration, Automation, and Response) solutions.
- PKI Auditing.
- IAM (Identity and Access Management) Tools.

The key elements for auditing of trust links can be listed as follows:

- **Regular Audits of Trust Relationships:** Auditors examine the lifecycle of each trust link to ensure that they were created, maintained, and terminated according to policy including if any suspicious activity occurred during their lifetime.
- **Compliance Verification:** Auditing ensures that trust links comply with internal security policies, industry standards, and legal requirements. For example, auditors check if encryption standards, identity verification processes, and access controls meet the required security levels.
- **Change Management Auditing:** Audits examine any changes made to trust links, such as policy updates, key rotations, or modifications in access rights. This ensures that changes are authorized and properly logged.
- **Access Control and Role Management Audits:** Auditors evaluate how access was granted, modified, or revoked via trust links. They ensure that only authorized entities can establish or maintain trust and that no unauthorized access/access privilege escalation attempt occurs.
- **Event Auditing for Anomalies:** Auditing trust link events can help identify anomalies, such as:
 - Unexpected renewals or terminations.
 - Failed or repeated authentication attempts.
 - Sudden access to sensitive resources without corresponding policy changes.
 - Security Incident Auditing.

In case of a security breach, auditors can review trust link logs to identify the entry point or compromised trust relationships. This helps in forensic investigations and response efforts.

In the iTrust6G trust model design, accounting and auditing trust links are crucial for ensuring the security, transparency, and compliance of trust relationships within a system. Accounting ensures that all actions related to trust links are recorded for operational management, while auditing ensures those actions comply

with policies and regulations and helps detect and prevent security breaches.

4 Policy Design and Modelling

4.1 Security policies and risk management

In the iTrust6G project, the security objectives will be specified as intents. Even if the use of intents and Intent-based Networking and Security are already considered significant improvements as they separate the security specification from the way mechanisms are enforced at a low level, we assume that this scenario can be further improved (at least) in a specific field.

Intents are typically the result of an implicit or explicit interpretation of the risk scenario and the generation of the corresponding mitigation. Indeed, these intents are used (and will be generated in iTrust6G) to generate the identification and configuration of the security controls available to meet them. In the end, security intents are an efficient way to specify and then enforce mitigations to security risks. In short, security requirements are considered separate from the risk management process each information system should implement.

Moreover, intent realignment is the process that remediates situations that make intents no longer enforced, by correcting deviations from the expected security level. Also, in this case, we can interpret realignment as the implementation of a new mitigation to cope with a new security scenario that has introduced new risks or modified the impact of existing risks to levels that are considered unacceptable. Two examples of this process correspond to the identification of a new vulnerability, or to the addition of a new service and its corresponding policies.

iTrust6G aims to obtain integrated management of security (intents) and risks. For this purpose, the iTrust6G framework includes a Risk Assessment Module (RAM), which is in charge of evaluating the risks in the information system.

However, the RAM, together with analyzing risks in the original landscape, can be used for assessing risks after some changes in the current scenario, that is:

- After specific modifications of the threat landscape (e.g., new threat intelligence reports).
- Whenever a specific remediation (described as a playbook) is implemented.

This component will be investigated for managing network risks and implementing network security policies. Its extension to risks that are not strictly related to a networking scenario is under consideration.

4.1.1 iTrust6G tools and a usage scenario

The assumption to have a correct and complete risk analysis is important for the rest of the workflow. Indeed, we assume that the entity using iTrust6G to protect their infrastructure has performed a risk analysis. Nowadays, these assumptions hold in most companies because of laws and regulations and because of a higher understanding of the cybersecurity landscape. Hence, if the risk analysis has been performed following the approach proposed by NIST in their Risk Management Framework (RMF) [37], or any other almost equivalent alternatives like the ENISA Risk Framework [38], ISO21434 for automotive [39], ISO27000 certifications [40], or NIS2 [36], the company will have the results of the framing and assessment phases. The framing phase defines the context of the risk management plan, the objective, the threats actors to protect against, and the high-level strategy for dealing with all the risk management phases. Moreover, the framing produces low-level details, like formulas to compute risks and severity, as well as the rules to classify assets, threats, risks, and impact of mitigations. The assessment phase will identify threat sources and vectors, attack strategies, vulnerabilities and weaknesses exposed to attackers, etc. Moreover, starting from threat information, the assessment phase estimates the impact on the assets, both the ones directly affected and the other that are indirectly compromised (e.g., reputation, business continuity).

These data need to be made available to the risk assessment tools. Typically, these results of a risk analysis come in the form of a set of spreadsheets. In this context, we are interested at least in:

- **Assets:** the list of elements in the network that have a value for the entity performing the assessment (and their location in the information system).
- These assets may be material (corresponding to something present in the information system) and immaterial (like reputation).
- Assets should be complemented with information about their value for the company performing the risk analysis.
- **Attacker model:** the set of attackers considered relevant (e.g., script kiddies, state-driven hackers) and their skills. This information is used to decide which attacks are to be considered in scope and the probability that the attackers considered can actually mount them. They may refer to external standards like EPSS or CVE to estimate these values. With this information, it is possible to list all the attacks against the assets to be taken into account.
- **Damage scenario and impact analysis:** it gives an estimation of the damage that each attack.
- **Risk model:** the set of all the formulas to use to arrive at the computation of the estimation of individual risks and to aggregate individual risks for having an overall view of the security exposure of the entity using iTrust6G.
- **Mitigation model:** the set of security controls available to mitigate risks and their effectiveness against data from the attacker model with the evaluation of their impact in reducing damages and likelihood of success.

4.2 Architecture for risk management

The diagram in Figure 4-1 presents the initial architectural details of the iTrust6G modules that manage the risks and their integration with the fulfilment of the intent.

Figure 4-1: The remediation selection and reinforcement tool and its relations with the RAM

4.2.1 The need for an active module

Since it is not reasonable to assume that the risk analysis reports include all the information needed for assessing the risks, we assumed the availability of a component to gather these data. The RAM foresees an active module that can complement the risk analysis information with actual network probes. The information in the risk model will drive this component, i.e., the active module will automatically understand which tool to use and how to gather the information required to compute the needed risk assessment formulas [41].

4.2.2 Risk assessment for intent fulfilment

Intents are expected to be refined into lower-level configurations, which are directly usable by the security controls that will enforce them, through a multi-level transformation process which adds more level of detail at each stage:

- **Intent processor:** it performs a semantic interpretation and enrichment of the security intents. They will be specified using natural language and, through the use of LLMs, will be enriched with the context and other semantical information. After this reasoning, intents may be internally represented using an intents specification language, like Lumi [15], before being translated into a security High-Level Policy (HLP). HLP will be expressed with a specification language tailored for the security requirements that will be supported (e.g., authorization at the service or network level).
- **Refinement Engine:** it contextualizes the high-level policies to the landscape (i.e., the networking scenario) where the intents will be enforced. This contextualization consists of:
 - identifying the security controls that can enforce the policies (e.g., VPN gateways for protecting the confidentiality of communications or firewalls to implement network authorization policies)
 - selecting the security controls that will be actually implemented, based on user-defined strategy (e.g., optimization of the performance or mitigation level, minimization of the impact in the network);
 - generating the configurations for the selected security in a security control-independent language named Medium-Level Policy Language (MLP).
- **Translator:** it translates the MLP policies into the actual configurations for the security controls.

In this context, risk assessment plays a crucial role in making the right decisions when selecting and configuring the security controls to use.

Works in literature have already presented models for refining policies, however, the factors that have been considered for the selection and the optimization of the decision of the elements to configure focused more on the performance of security control and on the overall performance of the network to protect. These parameters are essential, but they are only constraints in deciding the best way to mitigate risks. The approach proposed in iTrust6G, which aims to base decisions on risk information, should be able to mimic expert administrators in a real security context much better.

4.2.3 Risk assessment for intent assurance

When the tools monitoring the system have collected and enriched cyber threat information, the system may require an intent realignment process, which is a step of the intent assurance process.

The RAM can use this cyber threat information to recompute the new estimations of the risks. These new estimations can be used to evaluate if realignment is needed. Indeed, in the framing phases, explicitly

determining the threshold of tolerable risks is considered an essential step. If some thresholds are not met, the realignment can start.

In this phase, another component is involved: the Remediation Generator.

The Remediation Generator analyses the landscape, the threats, and the intents to be fulfilled and determines the remediation strategies to use. Remediation strategies are high-level landscape agnostic definitions of the operations to perform to reconduct the system to an acceptable level of risk.

These strategies must be contextualized to the specific landscape where they will be applied. The contextualization produces the Playbooks, which precisely determine the transformations to perform in the landscape and in the security control configurations to consider the mitigation fulfilled. This contextualization may use technology from the Refinement Engine, as it can be considered a special case of intent enforcement in a different landscape.

After the remediation strategies are implemented and the corresponding playbooks are produced, the Risk Assessment Module comes into play and reassesses the risks that would remain if a specific playbook were enforced. By evaluating the residue risks after the application of all the playbooks (together with the other functional parameters that will be considered in the design of the decision-making process), the Remediation Selection and Enforcement tool will decide whether the playbook should actually be enforced.

4.3 Policy representation for enactment

Policy representation for enactment involves creating machine-readable policies that can be automatically enforced within a system. This section focuses on translating human intent into machine-enforceable rules, ensuring compliance, security, and adaptability in dynamic environments. To meet modern security demands, policies must be granular, allowing for fine-tuned control over access and operations at the most detailed level.

The intent translation process converts high-level human goals and guidelines into specific, actionable policies that machines can execute. This process typically includes the following steps:

1. **Intent Capture:** Gathering and documenting high-level goals and rules from stakeholders.
2. **Policy Definition:** Converting these goals into formal, machine-readable policy definitions.
3. **Policy Implementation:** Deploying policies within the system to enforce the defined rules.
4. **Policy Monitoring and Enforcement:** Continuously monitoring the system to ensure compliance, addressing violations, and updating policies as necessary.

Modern applications, which are complex, distributed, multi-tenant, and operate at scale, face significant challenges in managing authorization. To handle this complexity, policies must be updated in real-time and designed to handle granular access control, defining permissions and roles at a highly detailed level to adapt to specific scenarios.

The concept of *Policy-as-Code* (PaC) is essential in addressing these challenges. Using declarative languages like Rego [42], authorization policies can be managed programmatically across multiple systems and environments. This approach offers significant advantages over traditional methods, where policies were manually configured through a graphical user interface. With PaC, policies can be updated and enforced with a high degree of granularity, making policy management more agile, scalable, and secure, while significantly improving the system's overall security posture.

Rego is a specialized policy language designed to express rules over complex data structures. It draws inspiration from Datalog [43] and supports a broad range of operations and data types, making it ideal for modern, data-driven applications where granular control is required. The key features of Rego include:

- **Declarative Syntax:** Rego enables users to define policies in a clear, human-readable format.
- **Expressiveness:** Rego supports complex policy definitions, including nested rules, structured data, and built-in functions that enable super granular control over user actions and resources.
- **Interoperability:** Rego can operate on JSON data, making it highly suitable for distributed and cloud-native applications.

As a reference, an example Rego policy is included below:

```
package example

# Allow read access to resources if the user has the "read" role
default allow = false

allow {
    input. user.role == "read"
}
```

In this example, the policy defines access rules based on user roles. The allow rule evaluates input data, returning a Boolean value that dictates whether the action is permitted. Rego allows this logic to be extended to extremely detailed conditions, enabling fine-grained control over which users can perform specific actions, on which resources, and under which circumstances.

Another crucial aspect of policy management is the policy lifecycle, which involves creating, updating, reviewing, and decommissioning policies as needed. Effective policy management also requires granular policies that control access at a detailed level, allowing for precise permission sets for different users, resources, and contexts. For that reason, versioning policies becomes essential to ensure comprehensive control and auditability. Versioning allows tracking changes over time and rolling back policies if necessary, enhancing transparency and traceability, especially when handling granular policy adjustments that might evolve frequently.

Finally, to maintain policy integrity, it is critical to implement policy signatures. This ensures that policies remain untampered and originate from trusted sources. Given the importance of super granular policies, integrity mechanisms are even more vital to prevent unauthorized modifications that could introduce security vulnerabilities or break fine-grained access control mechanisms.

In summary, policy representation for enactment is a critical component of modern system management, particularly in environments where granular control is required. It ensures security, compliance, and adaptability through machine-enforceable policies. The Rego policy language provides a powerful framework for defining, evaluating, and enforcing policies in distributed and complex systems. Real-time policy updates, granular control, lifecycle management, and integrity mechanisms like versioning and digital signatures are key to maintaining a secure, flexible, and scalable system environment.

5 Policy Enactment and Enforcement

This section outlines the strategies for implementing access control within a system, detailing the key components and enforcement mechanisms. It is worth noting that we refer here to access in the widest sense, not considering only the admission control to connectivity facilities, or the possibility to read or modify a particular data repository. In this context, access control implies the decision on any interaction required by a specific network entity towards another entity, what constitutes the practical implementation of the trust assessment process.

5.1 Implementation strategies

In today's cybersecurity landscape, where data management is paramount, the development of advanced methods to prevent unauthorized access to the system as a whole, and especially to the relevant data conforming its operational parameters, is essential. Traditional security measures are increasingly inadequate in the face of evolving service architectures, interaction patterns, cyber threats, and sophisticated attack vectors. Access control mechanisms must put a particular emphasis on standards for secure access management flexible enough to address the diversity and evolutionary aspects of the future network services considered by iTrust6G.

The reference standard for access control mechanisms is the OAuth [20] framework, analyzing its effectiveness and the widespread adoption of these methods. The study aligns with the objectives of the WIMSE (Workload Identity in Multi-Service Environments) IETF working group [44], which addresses the complexities of fine-grained, least-privilege access control for workloads deployed across multiple service platforms.

To define the iTrust6G access control framework several key components need to be considered:

- **Resources:** These are the protected assets that users request access to, whatever their nature and whether they correspond to physical or virtual elements, to services, applications, or infrastructure elements.
- **Users:** Individuals or entities interacting with the system, requesting access to resources or modifying/creating policies to align with operational needs.
- Depending on the context, a given network entity may be considered a resource or a user in a particular access decision process.
- **Identity Provider (IdP):** A logically centralized service for managing identities of the participating entities, typically implemented using protocols like LDAP (Lightweight Directory Access Protocol) [45]. This ensures consistency in identity verification across various systems and services.
- **Policy Enforcement Point (PEP):** The PEP intercepts access requests and enforces trust and access policies, ensuring that only authorized users can access the requested resources. The policies it enforces are defined by the Policy Decision Point (PDP).
- **Policy Decision Point (PDP):** The PDP evaluates access requests against defined policies and determines whether access should be granted or denied. It establishes the rules and criteria for access control, taking into account user roles, attributes, and environmental conditions.
- **Policy Administration Point (PAP):** This component is responsible for creating, managing, and modifying access policies. It allows for dynamic policy changes based on the needs of data owners or environmental requirements.

Figure 5-1: Architecture for enactment

- **Transparent Accounting Ledger (TAL):** It tracks access control activities, ensuring that all actions are logged for auditing and compliance purposes, addressing regulatory and security demands. The AL accumulates all decisions made over time, providing a detailed history of activities for later review.
- **Transparent Evidence Repository (TER):** This dynamic repository stores relevant evidence on any entity activities or scores produced by other entities in the system, providing data for assessing whether a particular request at a concrete time is according to the applicable policies. It is closely tied to specific interactions involving the referred entities, facilitating continuous and adaptive analysis of their status. The TER is intended to be the essential source of security attributes for the PDP to make its decisions, as well as support further analyses in auditing and explaining trust policy application.

Figure 5-1 illustrates the architecture diagram, including the components and their interactions.

5.2 Enforcement mechanisms

In the access control architecture outlined above, key components collaborate to manage authentication, authorization, and policy administration. To further reinforce these mechanisms, several improvements can be implemented, enhancing security, traceability, and control.

5.2.1 Identity management

The Identity Provider (IdP) serves as the central authority for managing entity identities, encompassing attributes such as roles, permissions, and other contextual information critical to the access control process. This repository functions as the primary source of truth for all entity-related data, which the Policy Enforcement Point (PEP) queries during both authentication and authorization processes.

In addition to basic user information, the IdP must collect and maintain comprehensive details about entities, including their assigned roles, group memberships, and any other attributes relevant to their access rights. This ensures that access decisions are based on up-to-date and accurate data. For example, role-based access control (RBAC) and attribute-based access control (ABAC) mechanisms rely heavily on the integrity of this data to enforce least privilege principles.

Given the critical role the IdP plays in the security framework, it must be highly protected to prevent unauthorized access or tampering. Any compromise to the IdP could allow attackers to alter identities, roles, or attributes, leading to potentially catastrophic security breaches.

5.2.2 Authentication, authorization, and accounting (AAA)

When a user attempts to access a resource, they must first authenticate with the Identity Provider (IdP), which verifies their credentials. Upon successful authentication, the IdP issues an access token that the user presents to the Policy Enforcement Point (PEP) to request access to the resource. The PEP then validates the token authenticity before forwarding the request to the Policy Decision Point (PDP) for authorization. This initial authentication step is critical for confirming the user identity, but it is equally important to separate authentication from authorization to improve security and ensure that access decisions are based on comprehensive, context-aware policies.

5.2.2.1 Separation of authentication and authorization

A key enhancement to this process is the strict separation of authentication and authorization functions. While the IdP handles authentication—validating the user identity—the PDP should be solely responsible for making authorization decisions. This separation adds a significant layer of security by ensuring that even if the authentication process is compromised (e.g., through stolen credentials), the PDP can still make robust, policy-based decisions regarding whether the user should be granted access. This division allows the system to implement additional controls and evaluate real-time factors such as user behavior, risk assessments, and environmental conditions before granting access.

5.2.2.2 Granular and context-aware authorization

Once the PEP forwards the request to the PDP, the PDP evaluates it against a set of predefined policies. These policies determine whether access should be granted or denied based on several factors, such as user roles, attributes, and contextual conditions. For enhanced security, the policies should be as granular as possible, supporting fine-grained access control decisions that reflect the principle of least privilege. This means users are only granted the minimum level of access necessary to perform their tasks.

Moreover, the PDP should be able to process a wide array of contextual information to make more informed decisions. For example, the PDP should consider the specific protocols being used, the type of resource being accessed, and the security level of the requesting device. This allows the system to adjust access dynamically based on real-time risk factors.

5.2.2.3 Enhanced policy management with version control

The Policy Administration Point (PAP) is responsible for the creation, modification, and management of access policies. To increase the agility and security of policy administration, it is crucial to implement a

version control system for policies. This system would provide a clear audit trail of changes, allowing administrators to track modifications over time, understand the reasons behind each change, and revert to previous versions if necessary. This capability ensures that policy changes can be rolled back in the event of misconfigurations or security incidents, thereby improving system resilience.

To further enhance policy management, all modifications to policies should be digitally signed, ensuring that no unauthorized changes can be made. This digital signing mechanism preserves the integrity of the access control framework and ensures that only authorized individuals can modify critical access policies. By combining version control with digital signatures, organizations can prevent unauthorized tampering and maintain a complete, auditable history of policy changes.

5.2.2.4 Comprehensive logging for audit and compliance

All activities related to user authentication, authorization, and policy decisions must be logged comprehensively. This logging should include detailed information about who accessed which resources, when, and under what conditions. The audit logs should capture all metadata associated with access requests, such as the protocol used. This level of detail is essential for both compliance purposes and forensic analysis in the event of a security incident.

To further improve accountability and security, logs must be immutable and protected with cryptographic techniques, ensuring that they cannot be altered or deleted by malicious actors. Implementing strong encryption and digital signatures for log records ensures that the integrity of the audit trail is maintained. Additionally, by capturing every decision made by the PDP—including denials—organizations can identify patterns of suspicious behavior, incorrect policy decisions, or emerging security risks.

5.2.2.5 Resilience and adaptability of the AAA framework

By integrating these enhancements—such as the separation of authentication and authorization, granular policy evaluation, version-controlled identity and policy management, and comprehensive, immutable logging—the AAA framework becomes significantly more resilient to evolving cyber threats. The separation of functions ensures that even if one layer is compromised, the overall system remains secure, while granular policies and contextual evaluations prevent over-permissive access.

Additionally, the detailed logging and audit mechanisms provide organizations with the tools necessary to quickly identify and respond to potential security breaches or misconfigurations, allowing for timely remediation. This also facilitates compliance with regulatory standards, as auditors can review the complete history of access requests, policy changes, and authorization decisions with full confidence in the accuracy and integrity of the logs.

Overall, these enhancements strengthen the system ability to adapt to complex, real-time security environments, providing robust traceability, accountability, and control. The resulting access control framework is better positioned to handle sophisticated cybersecurity threats while ensuring operational efficiency and compliance with industry standards.

5.2.3 Data flow management

Data flow management ensures that access requests are handled efficiently and securely, from initial authentication to final authorization and activity logging, as illustrated in the following figure.

Figure 5-2: Data flow for access control procedures

The access request process begins when the User provides their credentials to the IdP for verification. The IdP processes the credentials and, upon successful verification, sends the user information to the PEP. The PEP then queries the PDP to check the relevant access policies. The PDP evaluates these policies and returns an access decision to the PEP.

If the decision is to grant access, the PEP instructs the IdP to issue an access token to the User. The User then presents this token to the PEP to request access to a specific resource. The PEP forwards this request to the PDP to evaluate it against the defined policies. The PDP decision on this request is sent back to the PEP.

If access is granted, the PEP enforces this by allowing the User to access the Resource, initiating the requested interaction. Conversely, if access is denied, the PEP informs the User that access has been denied. This structured flow ensures that access is granted or denied based on rigorous policy checks and user authentication, maintaining both security and clarity in access control decisions.

6 Policy Accountability and Explainability

6.1 Accountability and transparency policies

As described in Section 2.4, accountability and transparency policies are necessarily based on the premise of complex 6G networks that require all actions and operations to be traced and audited to ensure that each entity is trusted. In this section, initial guidelines on how to achieve such propositions are presented. Concepts such as well-designed policies and automated compliance mechanisms are explored.

Firstly, the roles of each entity should be defined so that the interactions can be clearly defined. Network operators, service providers, and user entities should have a distinct and clear identity within the iTrust6G architecture. After that, each entity action should be traceable and auditable. As a result, the accountability of each entity in the network ecosystem can be provisioned at any time or autonomously. Moreover, if any unwanted action is triggered or discovered, the entity can be held accountable. At the same time, if the entity requires, those actions should be stored and presented in a transparent and non-biased method. Therefore, actions, decisions, and data flows across the network should be recorded and stored. Finally, storing the recorded actions should be considered as a required process within the accountability and transparency policy design. Maintaining an audit trail for actions to be accountable and transparent is of paramount importance on such policy designs [46]. In order to achieve the pipeline described above, some explicit actions should be defined, as to how the entities are identified and how the actions are traceable.

Regarding accountability, firstly, an identity management method/system should be implemented to properly verify the identity of each entity in the network/platform. This method/system should also properly define roles and responsibilities for each entity. This should occur so that if an unauthorized action is performed/discovered, each entity can be accountable for that and evaluated based on the roles that it should have within the network. On top of that, the actions that each entity is responsible for or has performed should be logged so that they can be audited by other components. These logs should also be aggregated for faster and more convenient analysis. This log auditing process could be achieved by either a real-time log analysis system or by timely, scheduled regular log audits conducted after an imminent incident occurrence.

Regarding transparency, data should be easily accessible and explainable to entities, if needed. However, security must not be compromised by enabling ease of access. Access control to such data should be limited with transparency policies that can define access control mechanisms based on the role and responsibilities of each entity. Moreover, explainability in AI systems, as already mentioned in Section 2.4, should also be implemented in order to provide human-understandable explanations of how AI decisions are made. This also requires the AI models to have some sort of transparency by providing the model's training data, assumptions, and decision-making logic. In addition, service-level metrics should also be captured while they operate, like uptime and service availability, and if needed, provided to the entities. Furthermore, if a service violates any accountability, or transparency scheme, the entities should be notified. This provides transparency so that the entities remain safe.

6.2 The role of transparent tracking: TAL and TER

Transparent tracking in the TAL and TER constitutes the base for a **notary service**, serving as a trustworthy record of evidence capturing the posture and behavior of dynamic elements in a given system, such as infrastructural components, applications, and users, during a given period of time. This record can be used to document and assess real-time security postures and system functionality, providing a reliable source of information in case of security audits, incident investigations, or operational analysis. This type of report is especially useful in environments where the behavior of the system components may change rapidly, such as in 6G networks and cloud-native environments.

Examples of relevant data to be stored by these notary elements, and for which a study on data models will become the next design step, include:

- **Software Bill of Materials (SBOMs):** A detailed list of components that make up a software system to enhance transparency and traceability.
- **Expected Measurements for Remote Attestation:** This includes data about the integrity checks for different elements before any required access permission is granted to them, ensuring the system components are secure and uncompromised.
- **Attestation Results:** The outcome of remote attestation processes, whether the system passed or failed, and what actions were taken in response.
- **Security Postures for Network Entities:** Detailing protocols and parameters in use, applied crypto technologies, versioning, and any other security relevant data for the network entity.
- **Security Policy Enforcement Data:** evidence of when, where, and how security policies were applied, including the identification of the subject, object and action required, and the outcome of the application.

These data, and therefore the access to the elements of the notary services, will be of use to:

- **Stakeholders:** Network service providers, infrastructure providers, third-party application vendors, and other stakeholders can use this data to ensure the system remains compliant with predefined security policies.
- **Operational insight:** The data provides real-time insights into system operations, resource allocations, and security status.
- **Auditing and governance:** Notary reports serve as the basis for compliance audits, governance policies, and operational reviews to enhance system security and efficiency.

7 Summary and Conclusions

This document, iTrust6G D2.3, is focused on one of the key commitments of iTrust6G: the application of policies to the trustworthiness issue in future mobile networks, as well as on the proposal of the functional principles for this application, dealing with the issues related to how policies are expressed (modelling), applied (enactment) and analysed (explainability). iTrust6G D2.3 explores the technologies foundations to address this commitment and identifies the next steps in designing and implementing the proposed solutions.

The document identifies and discusses four main technology pillars associated with modelling, enactment and explainability. These pillars include trust models and their design for modelling, intent declarations as the source for policy rules, enforcement mechanisms for enactment, and means for providing useful explanations of the application of these policy rules.

For each one of these technology pillars, the document analyzed the foundations for them, going into relevant architectural considerations and design guidelines applicable to each one in the subsequent sections, each one dedicated to the corresponding pillars. Based on these design fundamentals, the project team will start early technology evaluation, implementation, and integration work.

Given the core role of data flows in a knowledge-oriented approach as the one advocated by iTrust6G, the refinement of the high-level design defined in this document will start with the selection and further adaptation of relevant data models to be applied in the identified data flows, both internal to the iTrust6G platform (policy representation, evidence, decisions and logs, fundamentally) and external, focused in this case on intent declarations and explanation formats. Data models for the proposed transparent trackers, TER and TAL, will also have to be identified and adapted. These data models will shape how the selected technology solutions identified as base for platform development are applied.

The experience gained in these further work steps will guide the activity on a final version of the design, to become part of the iTrust6G architecture definition. The initial design presented in this document will be the base for early standards contributions, which will be further updated as the design evolves, and for industrial and academic dissemination.

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